

PROFILING THE GEODEMOGRAPHIC PICTURE OF EUROPE

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Abstract

The continent of Europe, as a localization for the development of modern human civilization from the most ancient times to the present day, has always been influenced by anthropogenic peculiarities that determine the number and movement of the population through the various geographic and historical segments of time events. The various factors of the nature of their situation have had a positive or negative impact on the number and dynamics of the human population of the Old Continent. In the report I make a chronological survey of the population, its number for a certain geographical and historical period. I analyze the current state of play of the public geodemographic massif of the continent Europe in the regional aspect for the period 2014-2018.

Keywords: Europe, geography, population, geodemography

Abstrakt

Der Kontinent Europa als Ort der Entwicklung der modernen menschlichen Zivilisation von der Antike bis zur Gegenwart wurde immer von anthropogenen Besonderheiten beeinflusst, die die Anzahl und die Bewegung der Bevölkerung durch die verschiedenen geographischen und historischen Zeitabschnitte bestimmen. Die verschiedenen Faktoren der Art ihrer Situation haben sich positiv oder negativ auf die Anzahl und die Dynamik der menschlichen Bevölkerung des Alten Kontinents ausgewirkt. In dem Bericht mache ich eine chronologische Übersicht über die Bevölkerung, ihre Zahl für einen bestimmten geographischen und historischen Zeitraum. Ich analysiere den aktuellen Stand des öffentlichen geodemographischen Massivs des Kontinents Europa unter dem regionalen Aspekt für den Zeitraum 2014-2018.

Schlüsselwörter: Europa, Geographie, Bevölkerung, Geodemographie

Résumé

Le continent européen, en tant que lieu de développement de la civilisation humaine moderne depuis les temps les plus anciens jusqu'à nos jours, a toujours été influencé par des particularités anthropiques qui déterminent le nombre et les mouvements de la population à travers les différents segments géographiques et historiques des événements temporels. Les différents facteurs de la nature de leur situation ont eu un impact positif ou négatif sur le nombre et la dynamique de la population humaine du Vieux Continent. Dans le rapport, je fais un relevé chronologique de la population, de son nombre pour une certaine période géographique et historique. J'analyse l'état actuel du massif géodémographique public du continent Europe sous l'aspect régional pour la période 2014-2018.

Mots-clés: Europe, géographie, population, géodémographie

Introduction

The population is variable, moving in a positive or negative direction depending on the historical and political events taking place in the area. The monitoring of the population during the periods of socio-economic development of the continental continent has always aroused the governing, regardless of historical time or concomitant events. Population numbers varied in range and factors related to the status of different ethnic groups inhabiting a given territory. Official population statistics began to be recorded relatively early in the eighteenth century, and in the twentieth century, it acquired the status of reliable information, controlled by the administrative governments of the countries. Nevertheless, monitoring the population movement, its number is necessary for analyzes and conclusions related to its socio-economic development. A number of authors from Bulgaria and Europe work in the field of geography (Beloch, 1900); (McEvedy and Jones, 1978); (Kremer and Michael, 1993); (Marinov, 2018); (Petrov, 2019).

The purpose of the paper is to study and analyze the geodemographic picture of Europe and to compare demographic statistics across continents with those of the world.

The study uses the statistical-mathematical method for analyzing the geodemographic status of the population of the continent of Europe, covering the period from the first representatives of the human species to the second two decades of the 21st century. The empirical method used in the report is a basic one that serves to collect and process information on the continent and the world population. The report includes an overview of the population of the Old Continent by region and other terrestrial territories using the comparative method over a period of time. I also apply historical methods in researching and analyzing dates, events, and processes related to material development.

Demography is a science that studies the population (human civilization), involving various social events and processes such as population, birth rate, mortality, natural growth, and migration. The term "demography" is formed by two ancient Greek words "demos" people and "graphos" description. The literal translation means "folk description". The changes that have taken place in the development of human civilization over the last 300 years require new interpretations, analyzes and studies of social events occurring globally. Geodemography appears as an intermediate link between settlement geography and demography. It deals with the study, study and analysis of these same socio-economic processes and phenomena caused by human activity in certain regions of planet Earth. A number of factors also influence the population: Natural - altitude, availability of natural resources, climatic conditions, relief, waters and others; Economic - financial crises, unemployment, job creation, investment policy, economic stability and others (Kolaj, Borisov, Osmani, and Skunka, 2018); Social - fertility, mortality, natural growth, migration, social infrastructure and others (Petrov, 2019); Ecological - air, water, soil, fires, landslides, floods, extraction of natural resources, industrial accidents and others (Yancheva, S., C. Yancheva, and Borisov, 2018). The conduct of hostilities in a given territory has a great influence on the population. High mortality in men in this type of process leads to lower birth rates and vice versa, after the war, birth rates rise sharply. Religion, as a spiritual and social element, has always played a significant role in the population. Within the boundaries of Europe during the various historical periods of development, the clergy used different religious practices and means to increase the population or

physically obliterate certain ethnic groups. Totalitarian regimes (Eastern European countries) experienced high population growth in the 20th century as a result of different social policies, one of which was to promote high birth rates, ban abortions, early marriages and other activities aimed at an increase in the proletarian mass. The population of human civilization, from the time of the Early Modern Man - Kromanian to the modern individual of the 21st century, is increasing every year. The exception is the periods of plague epidemics and prolonged hostilities, in which the population slows down its reproductive processes and decreases its numbers. Colin Peter MacDway, in his work, represents the number of people - 4 million who inhabited the Earth in 10,000 BC.

Results

According to the US Census Bureau's Historical Estimates of World Population (Kremer and Michael, 1993), humanity during the same period in the world is 50 million. by continents - Africa, 7 million, Asia, 33 million, and Europe, 9 million. For the rest of the Earth (territories) no hypotheses have been presented in the literary geodemographic sources.

Tracking the chronology of historical events, continental statistics, again based on the hypothesis - the population in 500 BC. the world is 100 mil. p., Africa 14 mil. p., Asia 66 mil. p. and Europe 16 mil. souls. Over the next five hundred years, there is an increase in the human population of fifty million. During the Holocene period, the migration (spread) of human species began throughout the world. During this time period the population is approximately between 1-3 mil. the person. Climate warming is an important factor in the growth and migration mobility of the human species over the above geo-chronological segment of the time cycle. From the tenth millennium BC by the end of the first millennium BC within 9000 the number of humanity has increased from 1-50 million. The first census in Rome (Roma-Roma), made in 435 BC, by administrative officials - censors. Initially, only the free people were enumerated, and subsequently slaves began to count. In 201 BC. the population of Italy, approximately 4 mil. p., like 1 mil. of these are slaves. Capital of the Roman Empire, 13 BC Roma have a population of approximately 800,000 people. According to modern estimates in 1 and 2 years of the New Era, it is estimated that the population of the Earth varies between 160-200 mil. souls. During the first decades of the New Era, the number of people increased in ascending order. The Greek and Latin texts that have reached us about Thrace and Moesia about the population of these two Roman provinces, in the first three centuries since the 27th century BC, to 327 AD., it probably amounted to about 3 250 000 people for the two territories. Karl Julius Beloch (1854-1929) takes the Thracian population at the time of Thucydides (455 BC - 397 BC) as a base, indicating a population of 600,000. From the first year of the New Millennium to 1000, the global population reaches 400 million. p., the growth within a millennium is 200 mil. souls. According to continents, Africa reaches 70 mil. p., Asia 269 mil. p., Europe 50 mil. p. in the latter the increase is the least compared to the others. In 1086, the first European census was conducted in England. Renaissance period XIV-XVII century, from Fr. - Renaissance Renaissance, embracing European cultural development, dating back to the dark medieval ages. The rejection of the Church's hegemony gives the population greater freedom to develop in different areas of socio-economic life. As a result, the population is increasing. In 1600, the world's population numbered 580 million. p., Asia 339 mil. p., Africa 114 mil. souls. In Europe, their numbers reach 111 million. or 19,14% of human civilization.

In the major European countries in 1600, the population was approximately, the following number - Italy 13 million, Spain and Portugal 10 million, France within its borders 16 million. p., England and Wales

4,5 mil. p., Scotland and Ireland 2 mil. p., Denmark 600 000 p., The Netherlands 3 million p., Sweden, Norway and Finland total 1,4 million e., Germany 20 mil. souls. Worldwide, the population in the 18th century is 682 million. During this period, Europe's population is 125 million. p., the growth of the previous century is an increase of 14 mil. souls. The low rate is the result of ongoing urbanization processes, the Industrial Revolution, and migration to neighboring continents. At the beginning of the nineteenth century, in 1805 the population of the world was already 1 billion (now the population of the population is 7 608 629 322 people) souls. In 1800, there were 3 cities in the world with a population of 1 million or more: London, Beijing and Tokyo. In 1851, London was the largest city in the world with a population of 2,4 million inhabitants. Official statistics on the population began to be kept in the Kingdom of Spain in 1857. On the continent, Europe reached 203 million in the same period. e. or within fifty years, there is a population growth of 40 mil. souls. In 1850 statistics accounted for 276 million, or within a century, the population has increased by 59%. With the development of industrialization, the use of natural resources and the cheap labor of the colonies, and the rapid progress of urbanization, London's population increased significantly before WWII, reaching 8,6 million. souls.

In the 19th century, London was the only city in the world with a population of 5 million inhabitants. Today, there are 55 cities globally, most of them in continent Asia. In the early 20th century, the population of the Old Continent reached 408 million. within fifty years, saturation rose by 132 million souls. In the world in 1900 the population was 1,650 mil. souls. In Europe, the number reaches 408 million. and constitutes 24,7% of human civilization.

The twentieth century was accompanied by two world wars that resulted in millions of human casualties. In 1916, Europe's population was approximately 330 million souls. After the war periods the population is recovering and increasing in number. In 1930, the world's population was 2 billion. In front of military Europe, human civilization on the continent is approximately 520 million souls. Five years after the end of WWII in 1950, the population of the Old Continent is 549 million. p., globally, approximately 2,5 billion people. In the mid-fifties, Europe numbered 577 1103 60 people, with urbanization accounting for 54,3% or 313 280 048 people living in cities. By the end of the twentieth century, Europe's population was growing in ascending fashion over the course of 45 years, increasing by 150 090 579 people.

At the beginning of the 21st century, Europe's population was 727,200,939. The continent's largest increase over the five years 1960-1965 was 294,067,977. In 2010, Europe's population was already 737,163,580, with 73% located in urban areas, with an average density of square kilometers. 72,9 people. According to the UN, the population of Europe in 2015 is estimated at 741 million p., which is just under 11% of the world's population. The exact figure depends on the precise definition of the geographical scope of Europe. In 2015, the EU population was 509 million souls. Non-EU countries located in Europe as a whole include 94 million souls. Five transcontinental countries have a total of 247 mil. of which about half live in Europe.

In the Table. 1 shows the population of Europe by year and region (area grouping was done by Worldometers), tracking the evolution of the number in miles for a period of five years. For the sake of clarity, I have also referred to the EU population movement within the twenty-eight countries.

Table.1 Europe by years of regions and population of millions. Source: Worldometers and own calculation.

years	North	South	East	West	Europe	EU-28
2014	102574541	152820713	293532237	191283239	740210730	507011330
2015	103097292	152440653	293243708	192032306	740813959	508540103
2016	103642971	152172107	292885221	192746859	741447158	510277177
2017	104199623	151989290	292454364	193430576	742073853	511522671
2018	104761581	151860162	291953328	194072933	742648004	512777350

From the initial period to the end for Europe, the population increased by 2 437 274 people, with the increase rising. The EU also has an increase of 5 766 020 people over five years, but the Community is characterized by high east-west migration.

Northern Europe (United Kingdom, Sweden, Norway, Finland, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Iceland, Isle of Man and Faroe Islands), recorded a steady increase in population. In the period 2014-2018 the growth is 2 187 040 people.

Southern Europe (Italy, Spain, Greece, Portugal, Serbia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, Northern Macedonia, Slovenia, Montenegro, Malta, Andorra, Gibraltar, San Marino and Vatican City), during the study period the population in that region decreased with 960,551 people. The downward movement of the number is from the beginning to the end period. The main reason for the decline is the high migration to the countries of Western and Northern Europe and the population of childbearing age.

Eastern Europe (Russia, Ukraine, Poland, Romania, Czech Republic, Hungary, Belarus, Bulgaria, Slovakia and Moldova), statistics show a population decrease of 1 578 909 from 2014 to 2018. During the five years of the survey, the population declined steadily, with the main facts being migration, lower living standards and low average life expectancy.

Western Europe (Germany, France, the Netherlands, Belgium, Austria, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Liechtenstein and the Kingdom of Monaco), there is a growth spurt for these countries, minimal due to high migration from the eastern countries. Each year, more than 500,000 emigrants formally enter the countries mentioned above.

Conclusion

In 1960, the world's population reached 3 billion. In a 30-year period, the global population is growing by one billion people. The next increase is in 1974, the human population reaches 4 billion. The increase is by another billion within 14 years. On July 11, 1987, in Zagreb, Croatia, was born Matthew Gaspar, the 5 billionth inhabitant of the Planet. In this span of 13 years, the population is growing again with another billion people. The next jump in population is on February 25, 2006, with another billion, or 6,5 billion. In 2009, there are already 6.8 billion inhabitants on planet Earth. The psychological moment of growth comes on October 31, 2011, when human civilization already numbers 7 billion. In the late 1920 is, about 12% of the world's people lived in Europe. If demographic trends keep pace, their share could drop to about 7% in 2050, but it still stands at 716 miles p., according to the UN assessment.

As of May 9, 2018, according to Worldometers, the World population is 7 620 873 604, for the continent of Europe, it numbers 742 564 911 people, including the EU with a total of twenty-eight countries, as of the above date, Eurostat statistics reports 511 522 671 people to the Community.

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